

Emerging technologies: A double-edged sword for SME resilience in Southern Africa

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Abstract: This study investigates the dual impact of emerging technologies on the resilience of Financial Sector Small to Medium Enterprises (FSSMEs) in Southern Africa, addressing both opportunities and challenges within volatile market conditions. Employing a qualitative methodology, the study involved semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions with 36 participants. The sample comprised of 30 FSSMEs strategic heads and 6 FSSMEs regulatory representatives sampled from Harare, Lusaka, and Mbabane drawn from a population of 3,890 registered FSSMEs. The findings revealed that technologies such as cloud computing, machine learning, and real-time data analytics extensively enhance operational efficiency, enabling FSSMEs to respond with agility to market dynamics. The use of emerging technology is still extensively limited among FSSMEs in the Southern Africa. The study identifies critical barriers to adopting emerging technologies including high integration costs, lack of structured digital transformation frameworks, and significant skills gaps among employees. The study underscores the necessity for tailored support systems and financial backing to facilitate effective technology integration. This study aims to inform policy and capacity-building initiatives that enhance the resilience and competitiveness of FSSMEs in an increasingly complex economic landscape.

Keywords: Digital transformation framework, Emerging technologies, Operational efficiency, SME resilience

1. Introduction

Digital transformation (DT) has emerged as a critical strategy for enhancing organizational performance, particularly among small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) (Yikilmaz & Kör, 2023; North et al., 2020). Globally, SMEs are recognized as engines of economic growth, contributing significantly to GDP and employment (Omrani, 2024; Sagala & Óri, 2024; Amoah et al., 2021). Notably, the pace of digitalization among SMEs varies significantly across regions, with developing countries, particularly in Africa, lagging behind their counterparts in Europe, Asia, and the Americas (Egala et al., 2024). In Europe, SMEs are increasingly leveraging digital tools to enhance operational efficiency and market reach (Matarazzo et al., 2021; Müller et al., 2021). A systematic literature review by Sagala and Óri (2024) highlights that European SMEs are adopting digital technologies to optimize business models and improve financial performance. Similarly, in Asia, studies reveal that digital transformation is pivotal for SMEs to enhance core competencies and sustain competitive advantages (Hu et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2022; Lim et al., 2022). In the South America, the World

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Economic Forum emphasizes the necessity of digital business model innovation for SMEs to navigate global supply chains effectively (Allgood & Bernucci, 2024).

In contrast, SMEs in Africa face significant barriers to digital adoption. The OECD (2024) notes that while digitalization presents opportunities for economic growth, many African SMEs struggle with inadequate infrastructure, limited access to technology, and insufficient digital skills (Amoah et al., 2021). Furthermore, a study by Taiwo, et al (2024) highlights that despite the potential of SMEs to drive economic development, their digital transformation efforts remain stunted due to financial constraints and lack of supportive ecosystems. This slow progress in digitalization is concerning, given that African SMEs constitute a substantial portion of the local economy (Egala et al., 2024). The World Bank (2022) asserts that SMEs account for over 90% of businesses in Africa, underscoring their critical role in job creation and economic stability. Without a structured Framework, SMEs in developing countries may continue to struggle with digital adoption, leading to missed opportunities and stagnation in economic growth. The current study explored whether emerging technology presented threats or opportunities for the resilience SMEs within the Southern African Market.

2. Literature review

2.1. Emerging technologies and their impact

The rapid advancement of digital infrastructure, increased connectivity, and the growing volume of data generated by businesses are significant factors driving the emergence of new technologies (Pothineni,2023). The global push for digital transformation has accelerated innovation, making technologies more accessible and affordable for SMEs (Khurana et al., 2022). Additionally, competitive pressure compels SMEs to adopt these innovations to remain relevant in a volatile market (Troise et al., 2022). Economic globalization and consumer demand for improved services further catalyze the integration of emerging technologies, enabling SMEs to enhance efficiency, customer engagement, and operational resilience.

The term Emerging technologies refer to novel advancements that have the potential to significantly alter existing processes, products, or services across various industries (Cha & Kim, 2024). This includes technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning, blockchain, the Internet of Things (IoT), cloud computing, big data analytics (BDA), augmented reality (AR), virtual reality (VR), 5G technology, robotic process automation (RPA), natural language processing (NLP), cybersecurity solutions, quantum computing, drones, and 3D printing among others (Le Blanc et al., 2024). These technologies collectively enhance operational capabilities and provide innovative solutions, allowing SMEs to adapt to market demands and improve overall resilience.

Emerging technologies, particularly offer significant strengths for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in developing countries. Enhanced operational efficiency is one of the primary advantages, as AI tools streamline processes, automate tasks, and improve decision-making capabilities, ultimately contributing to better customer satisfaction (Adam & Alarifi, 2021). Additionally, emerging technologies often enhance resource efficiency, reduce costs, and create innovative insights, providing extra value to SMEs (Chaudhuri et al., 2022). For instance, through integrating AI strategically with human resources, SMEs can foster innovation and achieve sustainable growth (Choudrie et al., 2023), positioning themselves favorably in competitive markets.

However, several limitations hinder the effective adoption of emerging technologies within SMEs. A critical barrier is the high cost associated with integrating emerging technologies into existing systems (Almeida & Wasim, 2023; Hansen & Bøgh, 2021). Limited financial resources often prevent SMEs from investing in advanced technologies, despite recognizing their potential benefits (Venkateswarlu et al., 2022; Dörr et al., 2023). SMEs may also view investments in emerging technology as complex and unnecessary (Liu, 2023), creating a reluctance to adopt these technologies. Furthermore, a lack of technical expertise and inadequate skills pose significant challenges (Frick, et al., 2021). Limited training and the scarcity of experts in these emerging technologies drastically limit the potential for effective implementation within SMEs (Lemos et al., 2022; Chowdhury et al., 2023).

Furthermore, as highlighted by Choudrie et al. (2023), expertise is crucial for successful technology transformation and innovation diffusion. Resistance to change has also been discovered to play a vital role in overcoming the uncertainties associated with new technologies posing a new layer of complex human related challenges (Chaudhuri et al., 2024; Łabędzka, 2021). Effective policies and government support are also not always available in developing economies to promote implantation of emerging technologies (Soluk et al.,

2021; Dey et al., 2023). Thus, while emerging technologies present promising opportunities, addressing the limitations is crucial for SMEs to leverage their full potential.

2.2. Necessity of digital transformation

The necessity for a digital transformation adoption framework becomes evident when considering the unique challenges faced by African SMEs (Omol, et al, 2023). A tailored framework can guide these enterprises through the complexities of digitalization, offering structured pathways for technology integration and strategic alignment. The need for such frameworks is further supported by findings from Egala et al. (2024), which emphasize that organizational drivers significantly influence the adoption of digital technologies in emerging economies. Without a comprehensive framework, many SMEs may miss out on the transformative benefits of digitalization, risking their competitiveness and sustainability.

Digital transformation is not merely a trend; it represents the future of business operations, especially for SMEs in developing countries (Bouwman et al., 2019). As the global economy increasingly shifts toward digital platforms, SMEs must adapt to survive (Amoah et al., 2021). The digital landscape offers unprecedented opportunities for enhancing operational efficiency, reaching broader markets, and improving customer engagement (Wang, 2022). According to the OECD (2024), digitalization can enhance productivity and innovation, which are crucial for the sustainable growth of SMEs. In developing countries, SMEs contribute significantly to economic development. For instance, in Ghana, SMEs account for 92% of registered companies and significantly impact socio-economic development (Amoah et al., 2022). Digital transformation can amplify these contributions by enabling SMEs to streamline operations, reduce costs, and improve service delivery (Achieng, et al, 2022). The World Bank (2024) indicates that digitalization fosters stronger economies by facilitating trade, enhancing financial inclusion, and promoting entrepreneurship. As highlighted by Taiwo et al. (2024), those that embraced digital tools experienced improved resilience and adaptability. Therefore, it is a central argument of the current study that for SMEs in developing countries, digital transformation is not just an option; it is a necessity for survival and growth in an increasingly competitive global landscape.

2.3. Major digital transformation challenges faced by SMEs in developing countries

One of the fundamental challenges in adopting emerging technologies in Southern Africa is the lack of a digital transformation adoption framework for SMEs in region. The absence of a structured framework for digital transformation not only affects SMEs but also has broader implications for stakeholders, including governments and policymakers who aim to foster economic development (Sarfo & Song, 2021; Taiwo et al., 2024). The lack of actionable guidelines for SMEs to navigate the complexities of digitalization is a critical gap that needs addressing (Bradač & Huđek, 2023). This problem has become increasingly urgent since the emergence of new technologies which are revolutionizing how businesses are operated (OECD, 2024; Bradač & Huđek, 2023). The potential benefits of digital technologies such as enhanced productivity, improved customer engagement, and increased market competitiveness will be missed by SMEs that cannot effectively implement these innovations (Wang et al., 2022; Taiwo et al., 2024). Several scholars agree that this lack of a digital transformation framework is a pressing issue (Li, 2022; North et al., 2020; Taiwo et al., 2024) in cognisance of the critical role of SMEs in driving economic growth and innovation. Thus, the absence of a tailored framework for digital transformation represents a significant barrier not only to individual SMEs but also to the economic resilience of developing countries as a whole (Taiwo et al., 2024).

Furthermore, despite the clear advantages of digital transformation, SMEs in developing countries encounter numerous challenges that hinder their progress (Albaz, et al., 2020). One of the primary obstacles is limited access to technology. Many SMEs operate in environments where digital infrastructure is inadequate, making it difficult to adopt and integrate digital tools effectively (Nnenna et al., 2024; Tamvada et al, 2022). The OECD (2024) notes that poor internet connectivity and unreliable power supply are significant barriers to digitalization in Africa.

Additionally, financial constraints also pose a formidable challenge, and many SMEs lack the capital

required to invest in digital technologies and the training necessary for effective implementation (Petzolt et al., 2022 & Smith et al., 2022). According to Taiwo et al. (2024) the high cost of digital tools and services often discourages SMEs from pursuing digital transformation initiatives. This financial barrier is compounded by a lack of supportive policies and funding mechanisms tailored to the unique needs of SMEs (Sarfo & Song, 2021). Furthermore, there is often a significant skills gap within the workforce (Minor et al., 2024). Many employees in SMEs lack the necessary digital skills and competencies to leverage new technologies effectively. This skills deficit not only hampers digital adoption but also limits the potential for innovation and growth (Li, 2022; Ivus et al., 2021). As highlighted by Hu et al. (2024), the absence of a digitally literate workforce can stifle an SME's ability to compete in a digital economy.

3. Methodology

This study employed a qualitative methodology within a multi-case design and interpretivist paradigm to explore the lived experiences of participants regarding the impact of emerging technologies on the resilience of Southern African SMEs. Conducted between January 2023 and July 2024, the research focused on financial SMEs in Harare (Zimbabwe), Lusaka (Zambia), and Mbabane (Eswatini).

The target population for this study consisted of 3,890 registered FSSMEs which were specifically those registered with the central bank or the financial sector regulatory authority in the respective countries under investigation. This focus ensured that the study was limited to formally recognized entities, providing a more accurate representation of FSSMEs operating within regulated financial sectors of the three selected countries. Consequently, this ensured the relevance of the findings.

Using the purposive sampling, a sample of 36 participants was drawn from registered SMEs. This included 30 strategic heads and officials from these organizations, as well as 6 representatives from regulatory authorities in the respective countries. Data collection utilized a semi-structured interview guide tailored for SME officials, while focus group discussions were facilitated with strategic heads of SMEs. Three focus groups were organized—one in each country—comprising ten members each, resulting in a total of 30 participants engaging in discussions. Prior to data collection, the instruments were pilot-tested with three groups of five SME leaders from each respective country to ensure clarity and relevance of questions. Feedback from these sessions informed necessary revisions, enhancing the reliability of the instruments.

Additionally, the instruments were vetted by three research experts to ensure methodological rigor. This comprehensive approach to instrument testing contributed to the final data collection tools used in the study. Through these qualitative methods, the research sought to capture the deeper perspectives of participants, allowing for a profound understanding of how emerging technologies either pose threats or offer opportunities for resilience in the financial sector SMEs of Southern Africa.

3.1. Data Analysis Techniques

Data analysis utilized NVivo Version 15 statistical software package to rigorously explore qualitative data, facilitating the coding process and the development of relevant themes. Both thematic and content analysis were employed to ensure a comprehensive understanding of participants' experiences. Thematic analysis allowed for the identification of patterns and significant themes, while content analysis focused on the context and meaning of the data. This dual approach ensured a rich interpretation of findings, capturing the complexity of how emerging technologies impact the resilience of financial sector SMEs in Southern Africa. This study utilised multiple multi-focus group discussions with participants from the involved countries (Wu et al., 2023). Furthermore, the brainstorming approach adopted in session and this made the discussions more probing. Subsequent discussion questions were modified based on the responses collected in the first discussion (Wu et al., 2023). This made the process more thorough and deeper experiences were shared during the session. The focus group discussion guide was semi-structured, and questions kept on being modified to explore the interesting argument presented by participants. The majority of the findings derived from the NVivo analysis are based on the data collected during these focus group discussions, providing a comprehensive understanding of the research topic. The data from the focus group discussion sessions was complemented by data drawn from SMEs officials from the three respective countries.

4. Result and discussion

4.1. Result improving operational efficiency

Figure 1 illustrates the results of data concerning participants' perspectives on the impact of emerging technologies. The transcriptions from three focus group discussions (FGDs) and six individual interviews with officials were analysed using NVivo, leading to the findings presented in the figure. Key insights regarding the impact of emerging technologies revealed that data analytics enhances efficiency and service delivery, while also providing a competitive advantage. Participants noted that big data facilitates actionable insights and that machine learning improves understanding of customer behaviours. Additional prominent views are captured in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Extract of Emerging Technologies Impact Theme Development from NVIVO

Table 1 Theme 1: Improving operational efficiency

Theme 1	Sub-theme
Improving Operational Efficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost Savings through Efficiency • Automation of Repetitive Tasks • Cloud-based Service Delivery • Real-time Data Access • Enhancing Customer Engagement

Source: Field Data 2023

The methodological process leading to the production of Table 4.1, Theme 1: *Improving Operational Efficiency*, involved a systematic analysis of qualitative data using NVivo Version 15. Initially, transcripts from three focus group discussions and six individual interviews were imported into NVivo for coding. Thematic analysis was employed to identify patterns within the data, focusing on how emerging technologies impacted financial sector SMEs.

Sub-themes were derived through iterative coding, highlighting specific aspects such as cost savings, task automation, cloud-based services, real-time data access, and customer engagement. This rigorous process ensured that the identified sub-themes accurately reflected participants' lived experiences and insights.

Theme 1: Improving operational efficiency

This theme encompasses the various ways emerging technologies enhance the operational effectiveness of SMEs. Data drawn from three focus group discussion sessions along with insights from six government officials through individual interviews, indicates that by automating repetitive tasks, utilizing cloud-based service delivery, and enabling real-time data access, SMEs can streamline processes, enhance customer engagement, and achieve significant cost savings. Each sub-theme illustrates a critical component of this operational improvement.

Cost savings through efficiency

Focus group discussions underscored the importance of cost savings achieved through operational efficiency. The majority of the participants from all regions noted that emerging technologies significantly reduce operational expenses by streamlining processes and automating tasks. Members from Zambia and Zimbabwe in particular highlighted that emerging technologies such as the IOT leads to drastic improvement in resource allocation and the elimination of unnecessary expenditures enhancing their financial performance. Furthermore, officials in Eswatini pointed out that emerging technologies can lead to vast saving and these savings enable SMEs to reinvest in critical areas, supporting long-term growth and competitiveness. Collectively, these findings illustrate how embracing emerging technologies can lead to substantial financial benefits for SMEs in the region.

Automation of repetitive tasks

The majority of participants across all focus groups reported that automation significantly streamlines routine activities, such as bookkeeping, customer support, and compliance checks. Notably, participants from Eswatini and Zambia were particularly supportive of this view, highlighting how reducing human intervention minimizes errors and frees up valuable employee time. They emphasized that this efficiency allows staff to concentrate on strategic initiatives, thereby improving productivity. Additionally, officials in Eswatini pointed out that the effective automation of these tasks enhances service delivery quality, ultimately contributing to a more resilient operational framework for SMEs. Participants expressed their views clearly:

“Emerging technologies could help us work smarter and do some of this legwork for us.....”
(ESWFGDP2).

“I feel like technologies like machine learning could help us serve customers better through understanding their behaviors and automating much of the services known to appeal to customers.”
(ZAMFGDP3).

“But we need the training and skills to know how to correct reliance upon such tools for meaningful data collection for strategic planning as this could help.” (ZAMFGDP5).

Officials reinforced these sentiments, with one stating,

“Machine learning pinpoints patterns in consumer spending, empowered pattern further pinpointing and enhanced strategic planning for small businesses. This provides predictability, and automation can be put in place for those tasks that are predictable and redundant (ESWOP2).

Cloud-based Service Delivery

The opportunity to provide service through the cloud was a major advantage relayed by focus group participants. Most of the Eswatini and Zimbabwe focus group participants supported this technology, stating it offers access to remote digital applications and resources while providing a more sustainable and flexible option. For example, many stated that they can communicate in real time and collaborate for effective and efficient service delivery. Likewise, Zambian officials stated such opportunities lessen the cost of daily living and operating—SMEs can remain on standby for customer inquiries without even having to open their shops physically—which increases the quality of service for the country.

Participants articulated their experiences:

“Technologies like cloud computing could help us better store and access data, but we’re not clear on how to integrate it.” (ESWFGDP8).

“Cloud computing has optimized access and processing of information, giving us a leg up on the competition, but there’s still much work to be done in cybersecurity and general staff appreciation of such tools to ensure they’re getting the most out of it.” (ZIMFGDP9).

Officials added to this, stating that

“Cloud computing provides flexible analytics resources, which makes more sophisticated data processing tools affordable and available to SMEs.” (ZAMOP2).

“These technologies hold promise—integrating the cloud software is immensely useful especially as the business goes entirely paperless. There’s a lot of promise for using such technology and SMEs need to capitalize on this to bridge the gap between them and larger market giants.” (ESWOP1).

Real-time data access

Real-time data access emerged as a crucial factor for SMEs’ decision-making processes. Participants from all three focus groups noted that having up-to-date information on operations and market trends empowers them to monitor performance effectively. The majority from Zambia and Zimbabwe highlighted how immediate insights help identify areas for improvement, enhancing their overall agility. However it was also clear that such technologies were still quite new and not all SMEs had access to them hence limiting to impact they currently had in a broad scale.

Participants expressed the need for better access:

“We need real-time data to stay competitive. When we don’t have it, we’re working with old information hence poor decisions based on outdated information.” (ZIMFGDP1).

“Real-time data is great for us to be able to adjust as soon as we identify performance gaps, although not everyone can do that.” (ZAMFGDP7).

“Not having real-time data significantly hampers our ability to react to the evolving marketplace and adjust our strategies, which makes us less competitive.” (ESWFGDP2).

Government officials across the board reinforced this perspective, indicating that timely access to data supports strategic planning and ultimately drives better outcomes, allowing SMEs to remain competitive in rapidly changing market conditions. They further confirmed that in all three countries a limited number of SMEs have access to Real-time Data Access due to internal and external limitations.

Enhancing customer engagement

Emerging technologies were recognized by focus group participants as essential for deepening customer engagement. A significant number of members from Eswatini and Zimbabwe emphasized the role of AI-driven chat-bots and machine learning in enabling personalized interactions. They reported that analyzing customer data allows them to understand preferences better, leading to tailored recommendations and improved service offerings. Officials in Eswatini also commented that this heightened engagement fosters customer loyalty and satisfaction, contributing to lasting relationships. Overall, these insights underscore the critical impact of emerging technologies on enhancing customer engagement in the financial sector.

4.2. Challenges faced by SMEs in utilizing emerging technologies

Table 2: Macro challenges faced by SME in utilizing emerging technologies

Theme	Sub-theme
Theme 2: Financial Constraints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost of Adopting Technologies.
Theme 3 : Digital Integration Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of Cohesive Digital Framework. • Infrastructure Deficiencies.

Source: Field Data 2023

The data for Table 2 was derived from qualitative interviews and focus group discussions conducted with 36 participants from various SMEs across three Southern African countries. The transcriptions of these discussions were analyzed using NVivo Version 15, applying thematic analysis to identify key challenges. Initial coding revealed significant barriers that SMEs encounter, which were grouped into broader themes.

Through iterative analysis, the sub-themes of "Cost of Adopting Technologies" under Theme 2 and "Lack of Cohesive Digital Framework" and "Infrastructure Deficiencies" under Theme 3 were identified.

Theme 2 Financial constraints

This theme encompasses the various financial barriers that hinder SMEs in the financial sector from fully adopting emerging technologies. Key challenges include the cost of adopting new technologies and a general lack of capital to support such investments. These financial constraints significantly impact SMEs' ability to leverage innovative solutions for strategic intelligence, limiting their growth and competitive potential in a rapidly evolving market.

Cost of Adopting technologies

The cost of adopting emerging technologies is a critical barrier for SMEs seeking to enhance their strategic intelligence capabilities. Participants across all focus groups indicated that high implementation costs deter them from pursuing necessary technological advancements. Many emphasized that financial institutions often view tech investments as high-risk, making it challenging to secure loans.

“Access to funding is a significant barrier. Many financial institutions view technology investments as high-risk, making it difficult for us to secure the necessary financing.” (ESWFGDP4).

“We want to fully utilise these technologies but we have limited budget and we barely have enough to invest or chase after the most up to date technologies. As is always known, financial institutions are often reluctant to lend to SMEs for tech investments, seeing them as too risky.” (ZAMFGDP1).

“We are in the business of selling cash and we know how scarce the capital is, furthermore, I believe you are aware that we don't really have any proper credit systems in this country hence we spent what we have, there is hardly any funds reverse to grow our technological facilities.” (ZIMFGDP3).

The officials from Zambia commented on the reluctance of banks to lend for technology investments, noting that this perception hinders access to crucial funding. Most participants voiced a consensus that without financial support, they struggle to upgrade or adopt technologies effectively.

Figure 2 Extract of Challenges face by SMEs in adopting Emerging Technologies from NVIVO

Source: Field Work (2023)

Figure 2 shows the key challenges that are faced by SMEs in adopting emerging technologies. Data from focus group discussions and interviews were coded in NVivo, identifying key challenges faced by SMEs in adopting emerging technologies. The codes pointed to subthemes which included "Lack of Digital Framework," "Technical Expertise Shortage," "Resistance to Change," "Capital Constraints," and "Infrastructure Deficiencies." These codes were grouped into subthemes, revealing the primary obstacles SMEs encounter in technology adoption.

Theme 3: Digital Integration Challenges

This theme addresses the barriers SMEs face in integrating emerging technologies into their operations. Key issues include the lack of a cohesive digital transformation framework and infrastructure deficiencies that hinder effective implementation. These challenges impact the ability of SMEs to fully realize the benefits of technology, leading to ineffective utilization of available resources and limiting their strategic intelligence capabilities.

Lack of Cohesive Digital Framework

The absence of a cohesive digital transformation framework presents a significant challenge for SMEs in adopting emerging technologies. Participants frequently reported that the lack of clear guidelines from government bodies leads to confusion and uncertainty regarding the implementation of new technologies. Most SMEs voiced a need for structured support to navigate the complexities of digital transformation.

"One major challenge we face is the lack of a cohesive digital transformation framework. Without clear guidelines from the government, navigating the adoption of new technologies becomes confusing." (ESWFGDP2).

"The lack of a digital transformation framework is a major barrier for us. Without government guidance, it's challenging to understand how to adopt and benefit from emerging technologies." (ZIMFGDP1).

Officials in Zambia as well as Zimbabwe reiterated the necessity for a national strategy to foster technology adoption, emphasizing that without proper guidance, SMEs often struggle to innovate and remain competitive.

"For SMEs to thrive in the digital age, a cohesive national strategy is essential. Without clear guidelines and support from the government, many businesses find themselves lost when trying to adopt new technologies. This lack of direction stifles innovation and hinders our competitiveness on a global scale." (ZAMOP1).

"In my opinion, we need a comprehensive national and regional framework to support technology adoption among SMEs. Many businesses are eager to innovate, but without government backing and a clear strategy, they face significant barriers. A coordinated approach would empower SMEs to leverage technology effectively and enhance their competitive edge in the market." (ZIMOP2).

Infrastructure deficiencies

Infrastructure deficiencies, particularly regarding internet connectivity and power supply, pose significant challenges for SMEs in fully utilizing emerging technologies. Participants across all countries reported that poor infrastructure directly impacts their ability to implement and leverage technological solutions effectively. Many indicated that these deficiencies limit their capacity for strategic decision-making, as unreliable systems disrupt operations.

"Poor internet connectivity and unreliable electricity supply hinder our ability to implement and utilize emerging technologies effectively." (ESWFGDP6).

"The inadequate technological infrastructure in our country is a significant obstacle. Poor internet and power supply disrupt our ability to implement new systems effectively." (ZAMFGDP3).

“Inadequate infrastructure, such as poor internet access and unreliable power, severely impacts our operations.” (ZIMFGDP5).

“In Zimbabwe, I would love to believe that we have quite advanced mobile infrastructure, and most business is done on mobile technologies. However, when we talk about real business impact at a business level, significant investment is needed in both hardware and software facilities, and I don’t think we are there yet.” (ZIMOP1).

“I think the IT ministry and major players like EPTC and MNT have made significant strides to ensure up-to-date infrastructure improvements for SMEs to effectively adopt and integrate emerging technologies. However, SMEs themselves will need to invest at their level to integrate their activities.” (ESWOP2).

Overall, officials believe that while there are advancements in mobile infrastructure and ongoing improvements, significant investments are still necessary at the SME level to fully leverage these emerging technologies. They recognize the existing potential but emphasize that a collaborative effort between government initiatives and SME investments is essential for optimal outcomes.

Table 3: Micro Challenges faced by SME in Utilizing Emerging Technologies

Theme	Sub-theme
Theme 4: Human Factors in Adoption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ignorance of the capabilities of emerging tech. • Resistance to Change. • Lack of Technical Expertise.
The 5: Security and Privacy Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Privacy concerns. • Cyber-security Vulnerabilities.

Source: Field Data 2023

Theme 4: Human factors in adoption

This theme highlights the human elements that affect the adoption of emerging technologies within SMEs. Key challenges include ignorance of the capabilities of these technologies, resistance to change among employees, and a lack of technical expertise. Addressing these human factors is crucial for SMEs to successfully integrate new technologies and enhance their strategic intelligence capabilities.

Ignorance of the capabilities of emerging tech

The findings reflected that many SMEs struggle with a significant knowledge gap concerning the capabilities and benefits of emerging technologies. In the Zambian focus group, a considerable number of participants expressed ignorance, revealing that most were not fully aware of how these technologies could enhance their operations or strategic decision-making. Conversely, the Eswatini group seemed more enlightened, although a few participants still lacked understanding about specific applications of these tools. Meanwhile, the majority of the Zimbabwe focus group appeared to recognize the existence of emerging technologies, yet they demonstrated little knowledge of their practical applications within their organizations.

Overall, while many participants showed some awareness of emerging technologies, follow-up questions highlighted that very few had a comprehensive understanding of how to implement these tools effectively at the organizational level. This knowledge gap significantly hampers their ability to leverage technological advancements to drive growth and improve strategic intelligence, underscoring the need for targeted training and support to enhance their competencies in this area.

“The skills gap in the workforce is another hurdle. It truth be told we were really not well informed about these technologies. While quite a few organisations are utilising them, it is safe to say the rest of us are not yet informed about these tools.” (ZIMFGDP7).

“Many SMEs face a substantial skills gap, which affects technology adoption. We lack employees with the necessary expertise to implement and manage emerging technologies.” (ZAMFGDP5).

Officials from Zimbabwe commented that without a clear understanding of technology, SMEs miss out on valuable opportunities for improvement. Most participants expressed a collective need for education and training programs to raise awareness of technology benefits, highlighting this as a critical step toward effective adoption.

Resistance to change

The finding reflected that resistance to change was a notable barrier for SMEs aiming to adopt emerging technologies. Participants frequently noted that employees often prefer familiar processes and are hesitant to embrace new systems, which can stifle innovation and hinder effective implementation.

“Resistance to change within the organization is a rear barrier. As humans we often fear new technologies and prefer sticking to familiar processes.” (ESWFGDP10).

“Employees are hesitant to embrace new technologies due to fear of the unknown, which stifles innovation.” (ZAMFGDP7).

“Cultural resistance to change within our teams slows down the adoption of new technologies, limiting their effectiveness in strategic initiatives.” (ZAMOP2).

Officials in Eswatini emphasized that overcoming this resistance is crucial for fostering a culture of adaptability within organizations which the government is fostering through incentives like the industrial park. Most officials expressed that addressing this resistance requires comprehensive change management strategies to encourage employees to embrace new technologies and enhance their strategic intelligence capabilities. Policy change at government level was also suggested as a give driver for SMEs to overcome resistance to change.

Lack of technical expertise

A lack of technical expertise is a significant barrier for SMEs attempting to leverage emerging technologies. Participants across focus groups reported that insufficient skilled personnel hampers effective implementation and utilization of technology. Many emphasized the need for targeted training programs to develop the necessary skills within their workforce. Officials in Zimbabwe highlighted that this skills gap not only affects technology adoption but also limits opportunities for innovation and competitive growth, reinforcing the necessity for investment in human capital to fully harness technological capabilities.

“The lack of technical expertise hinders effective implementation of technologies, leaving many FSSMEs under-equipped to harness strategic intelligence.” (ESWOP2).

“There aren't enough trained individuals who can effectively use emerging technologies. This shortage leads to ineffective implementation.” (ESWFGDP4).

“The skills gap in our workforce is a substantial hurdle. We lack employees with the necessary expertise to implement and manage emerging technologies.” (ZAMFGDP5).

Theme 5: Security and privacy risks

This theme addresses the concerns related to security and privacy that SMEs face when adopting emerging technologies. Key challenges include data privacy concerns and cyber-security vulnerabilities, which can deter SMEs from embracing new technologies. These risks can undermine trust and hinder the effective use of technology in enhancing strategic intelligence and overall business performance.

Data privacy concerns

Data privacy concerns are a significant issue for SMEs looking to adopt emerging technologies. Participants frequently expressed apprehension about sharing sensitive information and the potential risks involved.

Many highlighted that the financial sector is heavily regulated, making it crucial to ensure compliance with privacy laws.

“Data privacy and security concerns make FSSMEs hesitant to adopt emerging technologies, especially those requiring sensitive data sharing.” (ZIMOP1).

“Data security concerns are significant. I mean we have heard of a whole organisation facing closure because of breach in their systems and this supports our apprehension.” (ZIMFGDP1).

“Many SMEs are cautious about adopting technologies due to fears regarding data breaches and regulatory compliance especially with the new data protection act in our midst.” (ESWOP1).

Officials in Zambia noted that these concerns often lead SMEs to hesitate in adopting technologies that require data sharing. Most participants voiced the need for clearer guidelines and frameworks to navigate these privacy issues effectively, emphasizing that addressing these concerns is essential for fostering trust and facilitating technology adoption. Officials also indicated that the new data protection act of Eswatini is also causing a lot of apprehension among businesses on sharing information using such technologies. However it was argued that the fears were unfounded since the act is actually present to ensure secured sharing of data across both traditional and electronic platforms.

Cyber-security vulnerabilities

The findings also indicate cyber-security vulnerabilities pose a critical risk for SMEs adopting emerging technologies. Participants reported that the lack of robust security measures increases the threat of data breaches and cyber-attacks. Many emphasized the importance of implementing comprehensive cyber-security protocols to protect sensitive information.

“Without the right security measures, it becomes difficult to implement and utilize emerging technologies, which are crucial for our strategic goals. We also know once your systems are breached the government or the courts offer no tangible solution so we tend to observe caution.” (ZIMFGDP5).

“The lack of adequate cyber-security measures makes us hesitant to adopt new technologies. Protecting customer data is a top priority.” (ZAMFGDP5).

“Cyber-security vulnerabilities are a significant concern for us. We need to ensure that our data is protected against breaches and that we comply with regulations to maintain customer trust and safeguard our operations.” (ZAMFGD9).

Officials in Eswatini remarked that without adequate cyber-security measures, SMEs risk losing customer trust and facing regulatory penalties. However this was the reason the parliament passed a data protection act in 2022 to ensure entities are well protected. Most participants highlighted that improving cyber-security readiness is essential for successfully integrating technology and enhancing strategic intelligence capabilities within their organizations.

5. Discussion of findings

5.1. Impact of emerging technologies in SMEs resilience

The findings from the study indicate that emerging technologies significantly enhance the resilience of SMEs in the financial sector by improving operational efficiency and leveraging data analytics (Mangla, et al, 2021). These advancements allow SMEs to optimize their processes, enhance customer engagement, and make informed strategic decisions, which is crucial for survival in a competitive market (Philbin, et al, 2022). The adoption of technologies such as cloud computing, machine learning, and real-time data analytics not only streamlines operations but also fosters a more agile response to market changes, as noted by several participants from the focus groups and government officials.

The theme of improving operational efficiency emerges prominently in the discussions, with cost savings being a central aspect. Participants from Zambia and Zimbabwe specifically highlighted how technologies like the Internet of Things (IoT) enable more effective resource allocation and reduce unnecessary

expenditures. This aligns with findings from Almeida and Wasim (2023), who argue that effective integration of new technologies leads to lower operational costs. Additionally, Eswatini officials emphasized that cost savings from adopting emerging technologies provide SMEs with the capital needed for reinvestment in growth areas, supporting long-term competitiveness.

Automation of repetitive tasks is another critical sub-theme that emerged. Participants across the focus groups consistently reported that automating routine activities such as bookkeeping and customer support extensively enhances productivity. This observation aligns with the literature, where Chaudhuri et al. (2022) highlight that automation can lead to substantial improvements in operational efficiency by reducing human error and allowing employees to focus on strategic initiatives (Sariwulan et al., 2020). However, the findings also reveal a need for training, as many participants expressed a desire for support in fully understanding and implementing these technologies.

Cloud-based service delivery further enhances operational efficiency by enabling remote access to digital tools and resources (Dutta et al, 2020). Focus group participants from Eswatini and Zimbabwe underscored the flexibility and scalability that cloud solutions provide, echoing the findings of the OECD (2024), which emphasizes that digital tools enhance service provision through improved communication and collaboration. However, challenges remain, such as security concerns and the need for greater staff appreciation of these tools, which can limit the overall benefits.

Real-time data access is critical for effective decision-making, as participants noted that up-to-date information empowers them to monitor performance and adapt strategies accordingly. This resonates with the findings of Taiwo et al. (2024), who assert that timely access to data is essential for maintaining competitiveness. However, the study also highlighted a gap, as many SMEs still lack access to these technologies, limiting their ability to leverage real-time insights for strategic decision-making.

The sub-theme of leveraging data analytics further reinforces the potential of emerging technologies to enhance SME resilience. Predictive forecasting, a sub-theme within this category, has been recognized as a powerful tool for anticipating future trends and behaviors. Participants indicated that while they see promise in machine learning for improving financial forecasting, there is a lack of understanding regarding its full application. This concern aligns with the findings of Frick et al. (2021), who emphasize that a lack of technical expertise poses significant challenges for SMEs in effectively adopting new technologies.

Moreover, market trend analysis, facilitated by data analytics, allows SMEs to identify shifts in consumer preferences and market dynamics (Telukdarie, et al., 2023). This proactive approach is essential for survival in a competitive landscape, as highlighted by several participants. However, despite the recognition of its importance, the study found that many SMEs are not fully utilizing these analytical tools due to limited training and support. This finding is consistent with the assertion by Venkateswarlu et al. (2022) that many SMEs may not leverage advanced technologies effectively due to a skills gap.

5.2. Barriers to adoption

While the potential of emerging technologies is evident, several barriers hinder their effective adoption within the financial sector. High costs associated with integrating these technologies into existing systems remain a critical challenge, as noted by participants across all focus groups. This observation corroborates the findings of Hansen and Bøgh (2021), who assert that financial constraints significantly deter SMEs from pursuing necessary technological advancements. The reluctance of financial institutions to view tech investments as risky compounds this challenge, as indicated by various participants.

Additionally, the lack of a structured digital transformation framework is a pressing issue. Without clear guidelines and support systems, SMEs struggle to navigate the complexities of digitalization (Sarfo & Song, 2021). This absence of a framework not only affects individual SMEs but also has broader implications for economic resilience in developing countries. Taiwo et al. (2024) emphasize that without structured support, the potential benefits of digital technologies such as improved customer engagement and enhanced productivity will remain unattainable for many SMEs.

Furthermore, the findings showed that skills gap among employees is a significant barrier to successful technology adoption. Many SMEs face challenges in developing a digitally literate workforce capable of leveraging new technologies effectively (Liu et al., 2020). This gap is echoed in the literature by Hu et al. (2024), who assert that the absence of skilled personnel limits the potential for innovation and growth within SMEs.

The findings indicate that the high cost of adopting emerging technologies is a significant barrier for SMEs aiming to enhance their strategic intelligence capabilities. This aligns with Almeida and Wasim (2023), who

emphasize that the financial burden of integrating new technologies into existing systems can deter SMEs from pursuing advancements. Many participants noted that financial institutions perceive tech investments as high-risk, echoing Hansen and Bøgh's (2021) assertion that such perceptions hinder access to critical funding. Furthermore, Venkateswarlu et al. (2022) highlight that limited financial resources prevent SMEs from capitalizing on the potential benefits of advanced technologies, reinforcing the participants' concerns about budget constraints.

Additionally, the reluctance to adopt these technologies stems from a belief that investments are complex and unnecessary (Liu, 2023). Petzolt et al. (2022) and Smith et al. (2022) argue that inadequate capital for digital investments, coupled with a lack of training, exacerbates the challenges faced by SMEs. Taiwo et al. (2024) further contend that the absence of supportive policies and tailored funding mechanisms limits SMEs' ability to pursue digital transformation initiatives. Collectively, these findings underscore the critical need for financial support and training to facilitate effective technology adoption among SMEs.

6. Conclusion

The findings of this study emphasize the transformative potential of emerging technologies in enhancing the resilience of SMEs in the Southern African financial sector. Technologies such as cloud computing, machine learning, and real-time data analytics offer substantial improvements in operational efficiency, cost reduction, and strategic decision-making. These innovations enable SMEs to optimize processes, better engage customers, and adapt quickly to market changes, which are vital for sustaining competitiveness. However, the study also highlights significant barriers, including the high cost of adoption, lack of structured frameworks for digital transformation, and skills gaps within the workforce. These challenges prevent many SMEs from fully capitalizing on the benefits of these technologies. To overcome these obstacles, there is an urgent need for targeted interventions, such as financial support, training programs, and clear guidelines to facilitate the digital transition. The successful integration of these technologies hinges on the collaboration between SMEs, governments, and financial institutions to create a conducive environment for innovation. Addressing these barriers will not only improve operational efficiency but also foster long-term competitiveness and resilience, ensuring that SMEs remain vital contributors to the region's economic growth. Ultimately, the study underscores the importance of a balanced approach that combines technological adoption with strategic support systems to unlock the full potential of emerging technologies for Southern African SMEs.

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